

COASTAL WETLANDS ENHANCE GREAT LAKES WATER QUALITY

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Keywords: coastal wetlands, water quality, nitrogen, phosphorus, herbicides, nonpoint source pollution, wetland values, Old Woman Creek, Lake Erie, tributary

INTRODUCTION

Coastal wetlands of the Laurentian Great Lakes are believed to play a beneficial role in reducing the concentrations and quantities of materials entering the Great Lakes from their tributaries. However, detailed studies to validate that role have been lacking, and thus the value of wetlands in enhancing Great Lakes water quality has not been considered when planning coastal development strategies. Many coastal wetlands have been converted to other uses, such as marinas and farmland. As a result, their natural capacity for buffering the Great Lakes from the effects of urbanization, industrialization, deforestation, and agricultural development has been greatly diminished. The primary goal of this study was to characterize the nature and efficiency of pollution mitigation over a range of hydrologic conditions and for a broad range of substances within a representative riverine-palustrine coastal wetland. The specific objectives were (1) to measure inputs of sediment, nutrients, and pesticides into the wetland from upland sources, (2) to measure the net outputs of the same materials from the wetland into Lake Erie, and (3) to calculate the annual and seasonal budgets of water, sediment, and nutrients, as well as differences in input and output concentrations of herbicides (Krieger 2001).

STUDY AREA

The Old Woman Creek Wetland is a relatively natural riverine-palustrine wetland consisting of the flooded lower channel and floodplain of the watershed. A highway bridge and causeway constrict the wetland near its juncture with Lake Erie, and a railroad bridge and causeway constrict it further inland. During the period of study, the submerged area of the wetland ranged from around 55 to 62 hectares, depending on the water level, and the volume ranged from around 360,000 to 600,000 m³. Land uses included 60% cropland, 25% forest, 3% pasture, 3% orchards and vineyards, 4% residential, 2% water, 3% transportation, and <1% commercial and manufacturing (Herdendorf 1997). Of the total watershed area of 68.9 km² (26.5 mi²), 85% is drained by Old Woman Creek, a second-order tributary. The wetland surface accounts for 1.4% of the watershed area. The creek and wetland open to the lake through a natural barrier beach. Upland storm runoff events create and maintain an open channel between the wetland and Lake Erie. During low flow periods between storm runoff events, heavy surf closes the beach and prevents the bi-directional surface exchange of water.

METHODS

From October 1987 through August 1990, stream discharge and water chemistry were measured at a U.S. Geological Survey gauging station on Old Woman Creek above the influence of the wetland water level. Those data were extrapolated to the remainder of the watershed. Wetland stage and water chemistry were measured near the confluence of

the wetland with Lake Erie. Net discharge at the mouth of the wetland was calculated from measurements of frequent changes in water level coupled with volumetric estimates based on the wetland bathymetry. Precipitation and pan evaporation were recorded adjacent to the wetland.

Samples for suspended sediment and nutrient analysis were collected upstream and downstream primarily with automated samplers every eight hours and were kept under refrigeration for up to seven days prior to retrieval for analysis. Only one sample per day was analyzed except during periods of storm runoff. A second auto sampler at each station collected samples for pesticide analysis during the spring and summer. Samples were analyzed for total suspended solids, total phosphorus (total P), soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP), nitrite + nitrate nitrogen, ammonia nitrogen, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), silica, chloride, and conductivity. Pesticide samples were analyzed for twelve herbicides and four insecticides.

RESULTS

The upstream and downstream discharges of surface water varied greatly from month to month and showed a weak seasonal pattern (Figure 1). Most months when upstream discharge was low, primarily in summer and fall, the barrier beach dammed the wetland, thereby preventing surface discharge to Lake Erie. The calculated upstream and downstream fluxes of water and chloride were nearly identical, indicating that atmospheric and groundwater inputs of the nutrients and pesticides directly to the wetland were insignificant. Loads of materials exported to Lake Erie were strongly correlated with the stream and wetland discharge (Figure 1).

Other than chloride, the measured substances showed either a sizable gain or loss within the wetland (Table 1). The loads of both total P and SRP were reduced as they passed through the wetland, with only 67% of the total P and 54% of the SRP exiting into Lake Erie. Likewise, only 79% of the nitrite + nitrate N left the wetland, but almost all (94%) of the silica was released. To the contrary, more suspended solids (12%), ammonia N (92%), and TKN (17%) left the wetland than entered (Table 1). However, only 86% of the total N, estimated as nitrite + nitrate N plus TKN, left the wetland because the total N load was dominated by the amount of nitrite + nitrate N. TKN contributed only 18% of the total N upstream and 25% downstream. The retention rates ($\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{-yr}$) based on a typical wetland area during the 1990 water year were approximately: total P 2.3, SRP 0.57, total suspended solids -750, nitrate + nitrite N 70, ammonia N -7.2, TKN -12.0, and soluble reactive silica 22.

Of the 16 pesticides analyzed, only the herbicides atrazine, cyanazine, alachlor, and metolachlor were found routinely each year, with maximum concentrations occurring in spring soon after planting. Seasonal peak concentrations were always two to three times higher in storm runoff water entering the wetland than in water exiting into Lake Erie.

DISCUSSION

Unit area yields of total P, SRP, total suspended solids, and TKN from the Old Woman Creek watershed are slightly lower than those of other southwestern and western Lake Erie watersheds, probably reflecting the lower proportion of its drainage area (60%) devoted to row crop agriculture than the other watersheds (76%-83%, Baker 1993). The wide variation in monthly, seasonal, and annual loads exported from Old Woman Creek is typical of creeks and rivers draining the western Lake Erie basin (Baker 1993).

There appear to be no published long-term studies similar to this one that involved intensive sampling of Great Lakes wetlands where upland tributaries and seiches play major roles in the wetland hydrology. The present study has confirmed the importance of the Old Woman Creek Wetland as a partial sink or transformer for sediment, herbicides, and a number of nutrients. If indeed other coastal wetlands surrounding tributary mouths perform the same functions, their collective importance to the mitigation of the pollution of the Great Lakes must be substantial. Therefore, the large-scale loss of similar tributary coastal wetlands over the past century must have resulted in the input of higher concentrations of plant nutrients and herbicides into the Great Lakes. The preservation and restoration of some of these wetlands might be a cost-effective approach to the enhancement of Great Lakes water quality.

Table 1. Upland discharge (m^3) and loads (kg) to Old Woman Creek Wetland, and wetland discharge and loads into Lake Erie, 1990 water year (Oct 1989 – Sep 1990)

	Load to Wetland	Load to Lake Erie	Load to Lake/ Load to Wetland (%)
water	22,485,000	22,413,000	99.7
total P	5,813	3,867	66.5
soluble reactive P	521	283	54.3
total suspended solids	2,700,000	3,010,000	111.5
nitrite + nitrate N	136,733	107,610	78.7
ammonia N	3,255	6,243	191.8
TKN	30,123	35,093	116.5
soluble reactive silica	154,104	145,121	94.2
chloride	974,000	1,002,000	102.9

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study was supported by grants from the Division of Natural Areas and Preserves of the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, and the Ohio Sea Grant College Program (NOAA Grant NA90AA-D-SG132, Project R/ES-4), as well as matching funds from the Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College.

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Figure 1. Upstream and downstream discharge (upper left) at Old Woman Creek Wetland and loads of total phosphorus and soluble reactive phosphorus (left) and forms of nitrogen (right) in 1989 and 1990